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Proportional Representation System Whether Significance for Bangladesh: An Analysis

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to ensure free, fair and credible election by adopting electoral reformation, switch from 'Winner Take All' (WTA) to Proportional Representation (PR) system. In Bangladesh the election process and election result both have been questioned. Nevertheless, election is one of the key components in ensuring democracy. Particularly the free, fair and credible election is one of the basic and crucial prerequisites and elements of democratic government and governance. Bangladesh, we found an under developed political culture, lack of democratic political organizations, institutions and practices in true sense. All these indicators have been almost failed to institutionalize democracy in Bangladesh. In this backdrop, this paper attempts to explain that, a switch from the current Winner Takes All (WTA) system to Proportional Representation (PR) system can reshape the election system by keeping consistency, because of the fact that the democracy means the rule of the majority but the minority can't be uprooted as well as Proportional Representation (PR) method can help stabilize democracy in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Proportional Representation System, Bangladesh, Election

1. Introduction

When we got independence in 1971 our intent was to establish democracy under universal suffrage. But after 50 years we are still struggling to stabilize democracy in Bangladesh. At present Bangladesh follows 'Majority system' that is also known as 'Winner Take all' (WTA) system or 'First-Past -the Post' (FPP) system of election. Under this system, the candidate who gets the majority votes achieve the whole electorate and form government. The remaining candidates are left with nothing and they have no value, even though some of them might have obtained only a few votes less than what the winning candidate did (Islam,2016). The existing electoral system often leads to unfair outcomes and it is the barrier to ensure free, fair and credible elections. Thus, instance of stabilizing democracy election works against stability and makes unstable political culture. But the main saying of the Proportional Representation system produces stable and fair outcomes and promotes to real exercise of democracy.

However, it is going to be the biggest question on the mind of all constituencies when will the election be free and fair? Gradually We are going too far from free, fair and credible elections. It is very disquiet for us that our constituencies are losing their interest to cast votes. Though the election is one of the key components in ensuring

democracy because they enhance citizen's participation in governance, ensures government accountability and encourages political competition (Larry E. Udu, Joseph Okwesili Nkwede , Ezekwe Emmanuel A. 2014). On the other hand, in 11th national election the chief election commissioner (CEC) has said that 80% voters have exercised their franchise (Bdnews24,2018). But there is huge gap between balloting figures of election day and the number of casting votes which is not acceptable (**Dainik Sangram** ,2019). So how could we expect free, fair and credible elections? How could we ensure actual democracy?

Though, more than 100 political parties exist in Bangladesh now. However, two major political allies. Besides this, Bangladesh has mostly a fading two-party system, which means that there are two dominant political parties, with extreme difficulty for anybody to achieve electoral success under the banner of another party (Shakil, Kaniz, 2013). But currently both are heading coalitions of like-minded parties with the AL leading Grand Alliance formed with seven minor parties were deciding to participate in 11th national election BNP along with some other minor parties formed an alliance named Jatiya Oikya Front (National Unity Front) took part in this election (The Independent, 2020). Minor parties join these alliances to hold their existence as well as to save expropriating their security money. But the substantial fact is without minor party large party cannot form government in addition to before the election they use the minor party as polled tool. Nonetheless PR system which does not require political parties, through this system enable independent candidates to be elected if they achieve public support (Douglas,2014).

Furthermore, in the context of Bangladesh, there are few examples of female contenders are nominated and combat for a seat of national parliament like a male contender in national election. Our political culture and institutional structure are failed for women to attain a full role in democratic political system. Here female representation is 16.67% in national legislature. Among 300 seats, reserved seats for female are 50. These reserved seats are allocated proportionately over 300 elected seats in our parliament. In our parliament 300 seats are elected through First -past- the post system or Winner Takes All (WAT) system. As a consequence, vast number of electorates have no representation in reserved seats. It is clear that the exact extent of female representation is a consequence of an extremely complex and poor interaction of cultural, structural and institutional factors in our national context. There are few increasing curves of female participation and representation since our independence. Despite these difficulties instead of current electoral system we need to assume Proportional Representation (PR) system which can ensure largest possible representation and participation of females.

The paper is based on research and review of the relevant literature on Proportional Representation (PR) as well as secondary analysis of National elections on election results, participation, representation in national Parliament and its impact. This paper also examines whether a switch from the current Winner Takes All (WTA) system to the Proportional Representation (PR) system which can making Bangladesh election fairer and help Bangladesh stabilize her democracy.

2. Proportional Representation (PR) system: Conceptual Framework

The proportional representation system is an honored election system in modern states. For the sake of wider participatory democracy, there is a strong view in the community that the voting system of proportional representation (PR) sometimes also called "full representation" needs to be introduced for electing members of parliament.

Table1: Percentage of votes and representation of political party in the Parliament

Parliament	Date of Election	Votes (%) AL	Seats (AL)	Votes (%) BNP	Seats (BNP)
Seventh	12 June,1996	37.4 %	146	33.6%	116
Eighth	1 October,2001	40.13%	62	40.97%	193
Ninth	29 December,2008	49.0%	230	33.20%	30

Source: (Fioj,2003) and EC, Dhaka

More than 100 political parties participate in our parliamentary election. However, after a tough polled combat in the seventh parliamentary election the winning party got only more 4%, in eighth parliamentary election got only more .84% and ninth parliamentary election winning party got more 16% percent votes. Rest of the votes or constituency who were defeated party they have no value! for example, there are two candidates one can win with a minimum of slightly over 50 percent vote. The rest 49 percent of the voters who did not vote for that contestant failed to get their representation in the winning participant. But the principle of democracy is not the rule of majority but for all, which professes equality as its very root and foundation (Moniruzzaman, M. 2009). More precisely, what is looked for is the percentage equivalents between the total national votes cast for the respective parties' candidates, and the number of seats won by the parties in the parliament. Proponents of proportional representation believe that there should be a direct and close correlation between total votes cast for each party across the country in a general election, and the number of seats won by each party in the parliament. Under a pure application of the principle, if half of the voters in the country vote for the AL and one-third vote BNP, then half of the membership of the parliament - 150 MPs - should be AL MPs and one-third of the parliament MPs should be BNPs (Blackburn,1995).

Proportional representation (PR) characterizes electoral systems in which divisions in an electorate are reflected proportionately in the elected body (Mill,1861). If $n\%$ of the electorate supports a particular political party as their favorite, then roughly $n\%$ of seats will be won by that party (ACE Electoral Knowledge Network, 2014). The essence of such systems is that all votes contribute to the result, not just a plurality, or a bare majority. More precisely, the definition of proportional representation (PR) is an electoral system in which the number of seats held by a political group or party in a legislative body is determined by the number of popular votes received. In another way we can make clear that, a system in which the number of seats held by members of a political party in a legislature (such as a parliament) is determined by the number of votes its candidates receive in an election (Merriam website, 2020). The PR system, according to author Zama Shaikh, “aims at removing the defects of territorial representation “Under this system, all the sections of the people get representation in proportion to their number” (Zama Shaikh,2017). Even the smallest section of population gets its due share of representation in the legislature.” PR aims to achieve a balance between the share of votes and the subsequent share of representatives. If a party wins a certain percent of the votes, the same party should win approximately the same percentage of the parliamentary seats (Reilly & Reynolds, 1999). During practice it is revealed that the system does not produce proper representation. In Bangladesh perspective in case, there are two candidates one can win with a minimum of slightly over 50 percent vote. The rest 49 percent of the voters who did not vote for that contestant failed to get their representation in the winning participant. Representation of people continues to decline with increased number of contestants (The Independence,2017). Thus, of proportional representation (PR) system can create value of each vote and constituencies. Apart from this it can ensure the proper balance of votes and representative of the parliament.

2.1 Types of Voting System

In the world there are wide range of possible voting system. There are three common types of electoral systems used to elect government across the globe. These include:

1. Plurality or majority electoral systems

Also known as ‘first-past-the-post’ or ‘winner-takes-all’ a plurality electoral system is what we mainly use most of the democratic countries in the world. It’s a system in which the candidate(s) with the highest number of votes wins, with no requirement to get a majority of votes. (Arend,1985).

2. Semi-proportional systems

These systems are used in some local elections in the various countries. They tend to produce more proportional results than plurality/majority systems, but less proportional results than fully proportional systems. They include cumulative voting and limited voting.

3. Proportional representation systems.

These voting systems are used by most other advanced Western democracies and are designed to ensure that parties are represented proportionally (according to the share of the vote they win) in the legislature. They include

- A) party list systems,
- B) mixed-member proportional, and
- C) single transferable vote. (Charles,1999)

2.2 Types of Proportional representation voting systems:

A) party list systems:

Party list voting systems are by far the most common form of proportional representation. Over 80% of the PR systems used worldwide are some **forms** of party list voting. It remains the system used in most European democracies and in many newly democratized (Poundstone,2008). In these systems, parties make lists of candidates to be elected, and seats are distributed to each party in proportion to the number of votes the party receives.

There are three main ways to vote in Party List elections in use around the world.

- i) **Closed List:** Each party publishes a list of candidates for each voting area. On polling day, the ballot paper just has a list of parties. Voters mark the party they support. In this system, a party gets seats roughly in proportion to its vote, and seats are filled by the party depending on an order they choose.
- ii) **Open List:** On the ballot paper, each party has a list of candidates. In some open-list systems voters must vote for an individual candidate. In others, voters can choose between voting for a party or their choice of candidate.
- iii) **Semi-Open List:** In a semi-open list voter are presented with a ballot like that of an open-list system. The difference comes at the counting stage. Generally speaking, voting for a party is taken as an endorsement of the party's order and candidates are then elected in an order chosen by the party. However, with enough vote's candidates can be elected out of order, though this is rare (Electoral Reform Society,2019).

B) Mixed-member proportional (MMP) representation

Mixed-member proportional representation goes by a variety of other names, including "the additional member system," "compensatory PR," the "two vote system," and "the German system." This system was originally invented in West Germany right after World War Two, though since then it has also been adopted in several other countries. MMP systems in use around the world in 1999. It's a mixed electoral system in which voters get two votes: one to decide the representative for their single-seat constituency, and one for a political party. Seats in the legislature are filled firstly by the successful constituency candidates, and secondly, by party candidates based on the percentage of nationwide or region-wide votes that each party received. The constituency representatives are elected using first-past-the-post voting (FPTP) or another plurality/majoritarian system. MMP differs from parallel voting in that the nationwide seats are allocated to political parties in a compensatory manner in order to achieve proportional election results. Under MMP, two parties that each receive 25% of the votes may both end up with 25% of the seats, even if one party wins more constituencies than the other (Soberg and Wattenberg, 2003).

c) Single transferable vote (STV):

This system of proportional representation is known by several names. Political scientists call it "the single transferable vote." It is called the "Hare-Clark system" and "choice voting." Political scientists have long been advocated the Single Transferable Vote (STV) as one of the most attractive electoral systems. However, its use for national parliamentary elections has been limited to a few cases (Hill, Wichmann, Woodall,1987). Under STV, an elector's vote is initially allocated to his or her most-preferred candidate. After candidates have been either elected (winners) by reaching *quota* or eliminated (losers), *surplus* votes are transferred from winners to remaining candidates (hopefuls) according to the surplus ballots' ordered preferences. The system minimizes "wasted" votes and allows for approximately proportional representation without the use of party lists. A variety of algorithms (methods) carry out these transfers (Warren, 1994). Although the system provides representation to minor parties, results in single transferable (STV) elections generally have shown that minor centrist parties benefit from the system and minor radical parties are penalized.

2.3 Proportional representation voting systems in Different Countries

There are many different electoral systems in use around the world. At present many of the world including Europe, Asia and Africa already acknowledged Proportional representation voting (PR) system for nationwide **elections** Already many countries are considering or agree to introduce this system. In recent years, there are 87 countries practice Proportional Representation voting system to fill a nationwide elected body. Among the 43 countries most often considered to be within Europe, 40 countries use some form of proportional representation system (PR) to elect their MPs (Michela Palese, 2018).

There is a growing move towards the PR system. Some developed countries practicing the WTA system so far, such as New Zealand, are now switching to the PR system. Most of the transition countries, after noting the international experience of PR and WTA systems, have opted for the PR system. Even in the United Kingdom, there are now trends away from the WTA system and toward the PR system. For example, the composition of the newly formed Scottish Parliament and of the Welsh and Northern Ireland Assemblies and also of local government bodies of Scotland and Northern Ireland are decided according to the PR system. It thus appears that the PR system is emerging as the system of choice for the 21st century (Islam, 2016).

However, during the past two decades, various Asian states have made transition to democracy and turn towards 'Majoritarian Democracy.' Most of the states receive conventional First Past the Post (FPP) electoral system to elect their representative of legislature. In recent years, many Asian countries are concerned to ensure accurate democracy so that they are going to take initiative to change the electoral system that emerged on the political agenda. There are almost 12 countries among 48 countries that make choice of Proportional Representation voting system to elect a nationwide elected body.

On the other hand, all the nation states of South Asia make claims of being democracies, but this description merely affirms the fact that all nine of them hold elections of some kind (Himal Southasian, 2014). The practice of accurate democracy in South Asia still remains an unsuccessful dream. Actually, local democracy operates in South Asia. Most South Asian countries functions conventional First Past the Post (FPP) electoral system. But its show us linings that there is **an** increasing consensus among citizens and political parties in South Asia that the current First-Past-The-Post (FPTP) electoral system should be clanged. The best alternative would be Proportional Representation (PR) electoral system.

India has a bicameral Parliament of the Union (Sansad) consisting the House of People (Lok Sabha) and the Council of States (Rajya Sabha). The lower house Lok Sabha seats 545 members, 543 of whom are elected through FPTP in single-member constituencies the upper house Rajya Sabha can seat 250 members, 238 of whom are indirectly elected by the state's legislatures (Election Commission of India, 2020). Below are the results from the 2014 Lok Sabha elections. But the results of India (Lok Sabha elections 14, and 2019) clearly show the limitations of a FPTP system, especially in a country with such a large and diverse electoral base. (Himal Southasian, 2014). There is a growing consensus among a broad cross-section of citizens and political parties in India that the current First-Past-The-Post (FPTP) electoral system must be replaced. A Proportional Representation (PR) electoral system is one viable alternative (Misra, 2018).

Afghanistan has a bicameral National Assembly (Jirga) consisting of the House of Elders (Meshrano Jirga) and the House of People (Wolesi Jirga). The lower house Wolesi Jirga seats 249 members elected, through the single non-transferable vote (SNTV) system combined with a multi-seat single constituency, a peculiar amalgamation of two different systems that prevents political consolidation of their mandate by parties (Eli, Berman, Michael, Callen, Clark, Gibson, James, D. Long 2014). For Afghanistan the existing SNTV adequately addresses only gender inequality and partly ethnic cleavages. A better choice might be a closed-list PR system that jump-starts party formation and interethnic conciliation, as well as presents adequate representation of all ethnicities (Ghadiri, T. Sara, 2010).

Nepal has a unicameral Constituent Assembly (Sambidhan Sabha) that consists of 601 members, 240 of whom are elected through a direct, constituency-based FPTP contests, and 335 are elected through party list-based PR system. The remaining 26 members are nominated by the interim cabinet on a consensual basis. The Constituent Assembly (CA) has provisions in which women must make up at least half of the PR list. Overall, 33 percent of all the candidates for the CA must be women. Other PR quotas include 31.2 percent for Madhesis, 37.8 percent for the Janajatis (indigenous groups), 13 percent for Dalits, 4 percent for inhabitants of underdeveloped regions and 30.2 percent for others not mentioned elsewhere in the list (welcome to Election Commission of Nepal, 2020).

Sri Lanka has a unicameral Parliament consisting of 225 members, 196 of whom are elected from 22 multi-member constituencies, and 29 of whom are elected from one nationwide constituency. It consists of 140 Constituency Members, 70 District Members and 15 National List Members of Parliament elected for a six-year term. Sri Lanka follows an open list PR system in which each voter may cast three preference votes in a multi-member constituency. In this two-round contingent vote system, ballots whose first rankings are eliminated are redistributed to the next-ranked candidates if no candidate wins a majority in the first round of counting (Election Commission of Srilanka, 2019). Rest of the South Asian countries like Pakistan, Bhutan, Burma, Maldives has run conventional First Past the Post (FPP) electoral system.

As discuss above we can say, Proportional Representation (PR) system is becoming contemporarily significant may be for following manner. last 100 years have been away from Winner Taken All (WTA) voting system is running worldwide but last few years, PR was adopted in many countries. PR is becoming honored system to 'one man/one vote' principle of PR that is to say that every vote has its own value. Earth-wide among Europe, Africa, Asia even South Asia's most countries want to change their conventional electoral system due to ensure parliament institutionalization, to make democracy fairer, functional and fairly representation.

3. Proportional Representation in Bangladesh

Bangladesh has a unicameral Parliament known as the House of the Nation seating 350 members. These 300 members are directly elected from single-member constituencies through the FPTP system. The remaining 50 seats are reserved for women who are elected by the member of the house. This is done on the basis of proportional representation (PR) through single transferable vote (STV) in which the voter ranks candidates preferentially, and votes are reallocated from ballots whose first rankings are eliminated, shifting to the next-ranked candidates on those ballots (Ahmed, 2013).

Bangladesh at present follows 'Majority System' (MS) of national election. It is sometimes also known as the 'Winner Takes All' system or the "First Past the Post" system. The development of national election in our country is frustrating. The journey towards democracy is not a novel phenomenon in Bangladesh. The people of Bangladesh struggled for democratic political system for long years. Election culture of our country is skepticism demonic. Consistently Pakistan rulership, after independence, even when the democratic regime started journey in ninety decades always election result was questioned. Almost every election result denied by the defeated party with thin, uncouth fetch. The role of the government and the opposition was not conducive to democratizing the political system through free and fair elections and institutionalization during the recent past. Lately acceptability of election results facing criticism specially 10th election and 11th election, because these two-election held voter less and without appropriate participation of opposition. Which interrupting to stabilize democracy in our country.

From the perspective of political science, a unique 11th national parliament started its journey. There are several other issues related to reforms of the electoral system and electoral processes, which needs discussion and debate. Now **it's** time to think out of the box.

Firstly:

Proposals for reforming the electoral system, most notably proposals for changing the First Past the Post (FPTP) system, need greater scrutiny and debate. Further research on the pros and cons of different types of electoral systems such as Proportional Representation (PR) system and their implications in the specific context of Bangladesh politics are needed before initiating any reforms of the electoral system. A change of the electoral system may not necessarily lead to any improvement and worse still may lead to additional undemocratic practices.

Secondly:

In our country we see huge pressure pre- election and post- election context, for manipulation for winning the elections in the WTA system. This system always tries to abuse the voting process in several ways. But the PR system serves a direct link between the local vote outcome and whether or not the local political leader gets elected to the parliament. Hence, local political actors would not have as much stake in the local voting outcomes as they have now. Not only that, the decrease in pressure for manipulation and abuse of the voting process will undercut the importance of muscle and money power. Elections under PR therefore may not be as dependent on **terrorist act** as they are now. Furthermore, under the PR system, there would be little scope and incentive to manipulate election through resetting the boundaries of constituencies (Daily Star, 2014).

Thirdly:

The rate of Bangladeshi women's participation into our parliament and advancement of politics has been very slow and extremely poor. Today, women's participation in politics is necessary for both the democratic development of the country, as well as women's empowerment in Bangladesh. Critics argue this is a consequence of a number of factors, including women's responsibilities for family and children, the negative attitudes and discrimination of political parties, conservative religious and cultural doctrines, discriminatory socio-economic conditions, electoral systems, the nature of a regime and financial barriers (Rule, 1994a, 1994b; Liswood, 1999; Harris, 2001). Recently-held 11th general election, 22 women were directly elected among in 299 constituencies. Despite this, the percentage of women elected to parliament is less than 8% not even reaching double digits. With 50 seats already reserved for women, the total percentage of female representatives stands at 20.3% (Dhaka Tribune,2019).

PR can result in fairer representation for women. A series of studies since the mid-1980s have confirmed that more women have usually been elected to parliament under party list proportional representation (PR) than under majoritarian electoral systems (Norris, 1985; Matland, 1998; Reynolds, 1999; Kenworthy and Malami, 1999; Siaroff, 2000; 2001). This pattern holds both within established democracies and also across a broader range of developing societies worldwide. Within proportional electoral systems, the mean district magnitude has commonly been found to be a particularly important factor, with more women usually elected from systems using large multimember constituencies (Norris, Pippa, 2006).

PR is likely to increase the number of women in parliament. Furthermore, PR fosters ongoing challenges to major parties, and thus complements democratic pluralism. It is instructive that women in countries that have introduced PR are three times more likely to win seats through PR than to win in the first-past-post system.

Proportion of seats held by women in national Parliament in Bangladesh from 2010 to 2019

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/730649/bangladesh-proportion-of-seats-held-by-women-in-national-parliament/>, accessed on March, 2020

Fourthly:

There are huge chances of manipulation for winning the elections in the FPP system. In this system election results cannot accomplish acceptability. Defeated party always accuses against winning party and boycott parliament. In 2018 last national election Jatiya Oikya Front (JOF) chairman Kamal Hossain said a “vote robbery” had taken place across the country. “We reject the reported results of this farcical election and are calling for a fresh election under a nonpartisan government,” (VOA,2019). This system also tries to abuse the voting process in many ways. But the PR system serves a direct link between the local vote outcome and whether or not the local political leader gets elected to the parliament. Hence local political actors would not have as much stake in the local voting outcomes as they have now. Not only that, the decrease in pressure for manipulation and abuse of the voting process will undercut the importance of muscle power and money (Daily Star, 2014). So, we can look forward that under PR elections will free, fair and credible as well as election results will acceptable to constituencies, winning even defeated party also.

Fifthly:

In democratic system the members of parliament play very significant role. Unfortunately, Political parties are often nominated candidate in the basis of their money and muscle power, at present retired Civil-Army bureaucrats get priorities instead of skilled, devoted, grassroot candidate. Through FPP system is often leading to the nomination of election unskilled and wrong kinds of candidate. In consequence of our parliament only increase in numbers and becoming unintelligent. In other words, state goes far away from public welfare. Moreover, in politics there are creating apolitical culture which is restrict to institutionalize democracy in Bangladesh. A switch to the PR system may also help nomination and election of better, more qualified candidates to the parliament. The PR system, by contrast, may create greater scope and justification for nominating better quality candidates. People all over the country would vote for the same party list. Hence parties would feel pressured to include in their lists people with national reputations. It is generally people with exceptional qualities who are likely to be nationally

reputed. Through a feedback process, the PR system may encourage people of better quality to join political parties and to be active in them (Daily Star, 2014). In proportional representation system, a candidate does not require absolute majority of votes to be elected. **Instead**, they must obtain a quota of votes, which is calculated in accordance with a statutory formula (know Your Council,2020).

Sixthly:

Since restoration of democracy after the fall of the autocratic regime led by Ershad in December 1990, none of the political parties was able to form the government on their own. Therefore, major parties started banking on small or name-only political parties, giving birth to the politics of alliance (The Daily Star,2018). At present political parties often have a tendency to form political alliance which became our democratic culture. After passing a long and tough journey, our political parties have become confined now within two great alliances, Awami League (AL) led 14 party alliance or Mohajote (with Jatiyo Party) and Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP) led 20 party alliances. Both the alliances are distinct differently by people as per their own political ideology as well as manifesto. Under the existing FPP election system, most of the smaller parties are become a part of these two alliances. Bigger parties reach out to small political parties to extend their alliance before elections and to strength their position in parliament. They attempt to dazzle voters with the number of small political parties in the alliance irrespective of their registration or their leaders and activists (bdnews24.com,2018). On the other hand, in an alliance few small political parties achieve election seats and most of the time smaller political parties draw in few votes. Consequently, small parties cannot be a part of 'power' without alliance with major parties. Faithfully translate votes cast into seats won, and thus avoid some of the more destabilizing and 'unfair' results thrown up by plurality/majority electoral systems. 'Seat bonuses' for the larger parties are minimized, and small parties can have their voice heard in the legislature. Adopting PR would finally allow for free and fair competition between all political parties. Supporters of minor parties are forced to either waste their vote on a candidate who cannot win; vote for the lesser-of-two-evils among the major party candidates; or not vote at all. In short, single-member district elections are rigged against minor parties and serve to unfairly protect the major parties from competition (Douglas J. Amy (2016).

4. Conclusion

This article examines whether a switch from the current Winner Takes All (WTA) system to the Proportional Representation (PR) system which can gives fair representation to all political parties and racial minorities. This system can reduce lack of participation of electorates in the democratic process. It can ensure more women elected and represented in the legislature. Through PR system our legislature will represent all the varieties of political opinion-not just the majority, it would not be 'wasting' any vote. All these issues making Bangladesh election fairer and help Bangladesh stabilize her democracy. The proportional representation system spreads in the countries of Asia and Africa, gradually outside the European countries. The system has attained popularity in this way in the entire world irrespective of developed and developing countries. The democratic countries are expecting that the foundation of democracy would stand on firm footing through this system. The culture of election in our country is filled with the notion of doubt. Though the democratic government system is introduced consistently in Pakistani period, post-liberation Bangladesh and even in the nineties the result of election faces question always on the issue of acceptability. The defeated parties have thrown the acceptability of election result into criticism in almost all the elections on the complain of sharp or acute, gross fraud. In its reaction they have boycotted parliament and made the road heated. Consequently, the parliamentary system is going to be ineffective. The opposition party is also joining in parliament session for short period to retain their membership after interval of ninety days to preserve their membership without going to the parliament to uphold public interest. Though the ruling party invites the opposition party in the parliament once again they are not taking suitable action. As a result, the opposition party is not responding. Moreover, unfortunately our electorates are losing their interest to apply their franchise, what we have seen our last national election (11th national election) as well as last city corporation election also. In order to get free from this polluted practice of political culture our election system has to be made more acceptable and people oriented. For this reason, we can introduce party list system in our country which is one of the systems of proportional representation. As a result, no party shall be able to get more seats in the national

assembly by getting fewer votes. Moreover, not only the two big political parties but other small parties would get scope to represent in the national assembly by getting small number of votes. The democratic system would be established in country through this method not theoretically but in practice.

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